

Paper ID	Paper Detail
PC1	Acuña, Silvia T, Castro, John W, \& Juristo, Natalia. (2012). A HCI technique for improving requirements elicitation. <i>Information and Software Technology</i> , 54(12), 1357–1375. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2012.07.011
PC2	Almaliki, Malik, Ncube, Cornelius, \& Ali, Raian. (2015). Adaptive software-based Feedback Acquisition: A Persona-based design. 2015 IEEE 9th International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS), 100–111. https://doi.org/10.1109/RCIS.2015.7128868
PC3	Aoyama, M. (2005). Persona-and-scenario based requirements engineering for software embedded in digital consumer products. 13th IEEE International Conference on Requirements Engineering (RE'05), 85–94. https://doi.org/10.1109/RE.2005.50
PC4	Aoyama, M. (2007, October). Persona-scenario-goal methodology for user-centered requirements engineering. In 15th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE 2007) (pp. 185-194). IEEE.
PC5	Cleland-Huang, Jane, Czauderna, Adam, \& Keenan, Ed. (n.d.). A Persona-Based Approach for Exploring Architecturally Significant Requirements in Agile Projects. In <i>Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality</i> (pp. 18–33). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
PC6	Dittmar, Anke, \& Forbrig, Peter. (2019). Integrating Personas and Use Case Models. In <i>Human-Computer Interaction – INTERACT 2019</i> (pp. 666–686). Springer International Publishing.
PC7	Dittmar, Anke, \& Hensch, Maximilian. (2015). Two-Level Personas for Nested Design Spaces. <i>Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems</i> , 3265–3274. https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702168
PC8	Dodge, Jonathan, Hilton, Michael, Metoyer, Ronald, Hunter, Josie, Smeltzer, Karl, Vijay, Catharina, \& Atkinson, Andrew. (2017). Deriving Age Diverse Personas from a Participatory Design Study on Home Electricity Feedback. <i>Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems</i> , 959–968. https://doi.org/10.1145/3027063.3053354
PC9	Hosono, S., Hasegawa, M., Hara, T., Shimomura, Y., \& Arai, T. (2009). A methodology of persona-centric service design. In <i>Proceedings of the 19th CIRP Design Conference–Competitive Design</i> . Cranfield University Press.
PC10	Lachner, Florian, von Saucken, Constantin, 'Floyd' Mueller, Florian, \& Lindemann, Udo. (2015). Cross-Cultural User Experience Design Helping Product Designers to Consider Cultural Differences. In <i>Cross-Cultural Design Methods, Practice and Impact</i> (pp. 58–70). Springer International Publishing.
PC11	Lopez-Lorca, Antonio A, Miller, Tim, Pedell, Sonja, Mendoza, Antonette, Keirnan, Alen, \& Sterling, Leon. (2014). One size doesn't fit all: diversifying "the user" using personas and emotional scenarios. <i>Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on Social Software Engineering</i> , 25–32. https://doi.org/10.1145/2661685.2661691
PC12	Malik, Sofianiza Abd, \& Azuddin, Muna. (2013). Mobile technology for older people: Use of personas. 2013 International Conference on Research and Innovation in Information Systems (ICRIIS), 97–101. https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRIIS.2013.6716692
PC13	Abd Malik, Sofianiza, \& Edwards, Alistair. (2010). Investigation of cultural dependency in mobile technology and older adults. <i>CHI '10 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems</i> , 3835–3840. https://doi.org/10.1145/1753846.1754065

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PC14	Mayas, Cindy, Hörold, Stephan, \& Krömker, Heidi. (2016). Personas for Requirements Engineering. In Usability- and Accessibility-Focused Requirements Engineering (pp. 34–46). Springer International Publishing.
PC15	Mead, Nancy, Shull, Forrest, Spears, Janine, Heibl, Stefan, Weber, Sam, \& Cleland-Huang, Jane. (2017). Crowd Sourcing the Creation of Personae Non Gratae for Requirements-Phase Threat Modeling. 2017 IEEE 25th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE), 412–417. https://doi.org/10.1109/RE.2017.63
PC16	Mesgari, Mostafa, Okoli, Chitu, \& de Guinea, Ana Ortiz. (2019). Creating Rich and Representative Personas by Discovering Affordances. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 45(10), 967–983. https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2826537
PC17	Moser, Christiane, Fuchsberger, Verena, Neureiter, Katja, Sellner, Wolfgang, \& Tscheligi, Manfred. (2012). Revisiting personas. CHI '12 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 453–468. https://doi.org/10.1145/2212776.2212822
PC18	Moser, Christiane, Fuchsberger, Verena, \& Tscheligi, Manfred. (2011). Using probes to create child personas for games. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Advances in Computer Entertainment Technology, 1–8. https://doi.org/10.1145/2071423.2071472
PC19	Nunes, Francisco, Silva, Paula, \& Abrantes, Filipe. (2010). Human-computer interaction and the older adult. Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments, 1–8. https://doi.org/10.1145/1839294.1839353
PC20	Nunes Rodrigues, Genáina, Joel Tavares, Carlos, Watanabe, Naiara, Alves, Carina, \& Ali, Raian. (2018). A Persona-Based Modelling for Contextual Requirements. In Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (pp. 352–368). Springer International Publishing.
PC21	O'Flaherty, B., Pope, A., Thornton, C., \& Woodworth, S. (2013). Capturing multi-stakeholder needs in Customer-Centric Cloud Service Design. International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2013): Reshaping Society Through Information Systems Design. 1.
PC22	Porter, Chris, Letier, Emmanuel, \& Sasse, M. Angela. (2014). Building a National E-Service using Sentire experience report on the use of Sentire: A volere-based requirements framework driven by calibrated personas and simulated user feedback. 2014 IEEE 22nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE), 374–383. https://doi.org/10.1109/RE.2014.6912288
PC23	Queirós, A., Silva, A. G., Simões, P., Santos, C., Martins, C., da Rocha, N. P., \& Rodrigues, M. (2018, June). SmartWalk: Personas and scenarios definition and functional requirements. In 2018 2nd International Conference on Technology and Innovation in Sports, Health and Wellbeing (TISHW) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
PC24	Rahimi, Mona, \& Cleland-Huang, Jane. (2014). Personas in the middle. Proceedings of the 29th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Automated Software Engineering, 479–484. https://doi.org/10.1145/2642937.2642958
PC25	Schäfer, Katharina, Rasche, Peter, Bröhl, Christina, Theis, Sabine, Barton, Laura, Brandl, Christopher, Wille, Matthias, Nitsch, Verena, \& Mertens, Alexander. (2019). Survey-based personas for a target-group-specific consideration of elderly end users of information and communication systems in the German health-care sector. International Journal of Medical Informatics (Shannon, Ireland), 132, 103924–103924. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.07.003

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PC26	Sedeño, J., Schön, E. M., Torrecilla Salinas, C. J., Thomaschewski, J., Escalona Cuaresma, M. J., \& Mejías Risoto, M. (2017). Modelling agile requirements using context-based persona stories. In WEBIST 2017: 13th International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies (2017), p 196-203. ScitePress Digital Library.
PC27	Shahri, Alimohammad, Hosseini, Mahmood, Almaliki, Malik, Phalp, Keith, Taylor, Jacqui, \& Ali, Raian. (2016). Engineering software-based motivation: A persona-based approach. 2016 IEEE Tenth International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS), 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1109/RCIS.2016.7549312
PC28	Kifle, Mesfin, Dittrich, Yvonne, \& Teka, Degif. (2017). Contextualizing user centered design with agile methods in Ethiopia. 2017 IEEE AFRICON, 911–916. https://doi.org/10.1109/AFRCON.2017.8095603
PC29	Yu, Der-Jang, \& Lin, Wen-Chi. (2009). Facilitating Idea Generation Using Personas. In Human Centered Design (Vol. 5619, pp. 381–388). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
PC30	Aguirre, Joel, Falconi, Fiorella, Serrano, Rodrigo, Moquillaza, Arturo, \& Paz, Freddy. (2021). Improving the Withdrawal Functionality on ATM Using a UCD Framework. A Case Study. In Design, User Experience, and Usability: Design for Diversity, Well-being, and Social Development (pp. 565–580). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78224-5_39
PC31	Arenas, C., Garcés, L., Carmona, M. J., \& Simões, C. M. (2020, December). Requirements specification of a software-intensive system in the health domain: An experience report. In 19th Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality (pp. 1-10).
PC32	Askarbekuly, Nursultan, Solovyov, Alexandr, Lukyanchikova, Elena, Pimenov, Denis, \& Mazzara, Manuel. (2021). Building an Educational Product: Constructive Alignment and Requirements Engineering. In Advances in Artificial Intelligence, Software and Systems Engineering (Vol. 271, pp. 358–365). Springer International Publishing.
PC33	Ferreira, David, Melo, Daniela, Santo, Andreia, Silva, Pedro, Soares, Sandra C., \& Silva, Samuel. (2020). Stop Anxiety: Tackling Anxiety in the Academic Campus Through an mHealth Multidisciplinary User-Centred Approach. In Lecture Notes of the Institute for Computer Sciences, Social-Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering, LNICST (Vol. 320, pp. 112–126). Springer International Publishing.
PC34	Ho, Sui-Hua, \& Lin, Chiuhsiang Joe. (2020). The Requirement Analysis for Developing the Assisted Living Technology for the Elderly. In Cognitive Cities (Vol. 1227, pp. 563–568). Springer Singapore.
PC35	Jovanović, Mlađan, De Angeli, Antonella, McNeill, Andrew, \& Coventry, Lynne. (2021). User Requirements for Inclusive Technology for Older Adults. International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction, 37(20), 1947–1965. https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2021.1921365
PC36	Kabir, K. S., Alsaleem, A., \& Wiese, J. (2021, June). The Impact of Spinal Cord Injury on Participation in Human-Centered Research. In Designing Interactive Systems Conference 2021 (pp. 1902-1914).
PC37	Mueller, Alexander, Beyer, Stefanie, Kopp, Gerhard, \& Deisser, Oliver. (2019). User-Centered Development of a Public Transportation Vehicle Operated in a Demand-Responsive Environment. Advances in Human Factors of Transportation, 545–555. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20503-4_49

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PC38	Rivero, Luis, Portela, Carlos, Boaro, José, Santos, Pedro, Rego, Venicius, Braz Junior, Geraldo, Paiva, Anselmo, Alves, Erika, Oliveira, Milton, Moraes, Renato, \& Mendes, Marina. (2021). Lessons Learned from Applying Requirements and Design Techniques in the Development of a Machine Learning System for Predicting Lawsuits Against Power Companies. In Human Interface and the Management of Information. Information Presentation and Visualization (Vol. 12765, pp. 227–243). Springer International Publishing.
PC39	Spieler, B., Krnjic, V., Slany, W., Horneck, K., \& Neudorfer, U. (2020, October). Design, Code, Stitch, Wear, and Show It! Mobile Visual Pattern Design in School Contexts. In 2020 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE) (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
PC40	Wang, O., Cheng, B., Hoang, T., Arora, C., \& Liu, X. (2021, November). Virtual Reality Enabled Human-Centric Requirements Engineering. In 2021 36th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering Workshops (ASEW) (pp. 159-164). IEEE.
PC41	Whitehand, R., Albanis, G., Zioulis, N., Bailer, W., Zarpalas, D., \& Daras, P. (2021, June). Towards User Generated AR Experiences: Enable consumers to generate their own AR experiences for planning indoor spaces. In ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences (pp. 299-304).